

Standardized Data Literacy and Research Data Management Competencies in the Physics Curriculum in Universities

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PUNCH4NFDI
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1 Introduction

In recent years, the field of physics is part of a transformation shaped by the rapid growth of data-driven research methods as well as vast and complex datasets which are now an integral part of advancing knowledge. High-quality data are also a key prerequisite for artificial intelligence being part of future research, a new era which is called the 4th paradigm of science [1, 2]. In order to be part of it, students and researchers alike must acquire and exercise novel skills of data literacy (DL) and research data management (RDM).

DL encompasses a broad range of competencies, from data generation and storage to analysis, interpretation, and ethical and legal aspects of data sharing. For physics students, this skill set is essential. It enables them to understand and leverage data responsibly, ensuring their work is sustainable, reproducible and valuable within the broader scientific community.

RDM further enhances these competencies by focusing on best practices for managing data across its lifecycle. There is broad consensus that data should be organized along the FAIR principles, ensuring Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability [3].

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All of these competencies are intricately linked to and ultimately part of good scientific practice.

The German National Research Data Infrastructure Initiative (NFDI) is designated to establish RDM standards in all scientific disciplines. There are three NFDI consortia which have their core activity in physics: DAPHNE4NFDI, FAIRmat, and PUNCH4NFDI. The DAPHNE4NFDI Consortium is dedicated to research with photons and neutrons at large-scale facilities. FAIRmat is dedicated to Condensed Matter Physics and the Chemical Physics of Solids, and PUNCH4NFDI is dedicated to particle physics, astroparticle physics, astronomy, nuclear physics, and hadron physics.

As part of this mission, all three consortia jointly seek to support physics education by promoting competencies in DL and RDM. Recognizing the growing importance of these skills, they have developed this recommendation to provide a strategic framework for integrating data literacy into physics curricula, with the intent to complement the corresponding recommendation of the *Konferenz der Fachbereiche* [4].

The document highlights key integration points across bachelor's, master's, and doctoral levels to equip students with the data skills needed to succeed in both academic and professional environments.

2 Core skills for data literacy in physics education

To ensure that physics students are prepared for the demands of modern, data-intensive research environments and the complexities of data-driven research, we propose to integrate the training of the following skills into the curriculum to help students acquire essential DL and RDM core competencies:

Programming fundamentals Proficiency in programming, especially in Python as a common language including tools such as Jupyter Notebooks

Data acquisition Strategies for creation of simulated/theory data and collection of experimental data.

Data documentation Understanding the importance of metadata and the FAIR principles. This includes metadata standards and the use of Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN)s as a prerequisite of data that can be understood, reproduced, and reused by others.

Data analysis Familiarity with parameter extraction, statistical techniques, visualisation and techniques of machine learning.

Data storage Knowledge of advanced data formats (e. g. HDF5) and storage types.

Repositories Experience with repositories like *HEPData* [5] and NOMAD [6, 7] raises awareness for findable and accessible data spaces, but also introduces to the concepts of data interoperability and data publication.

Legal and Ethical Aspects Ethical data practices that are in line with the Data Literacy Charta [8], and the rules of good scientific practice [9] preparing students to work responsibly within large research teams.

3 Curriculum constraints and the need for strategic integration

Integrating DL into the physics curriculum presents a range of challenges, primarily due to competing priorities in traditional physics education. Physics curricula are already dense, covering foundational topics in experimental and theoretical physics, lab courses, and advanced mathematical techniques. These traditional areas provide essential skills and knowledge that are indispensable to a physics education. However, with the increasing importance of DL and RDM, educators face the challenge of finding space in the curriculum for this newer set of skills without diminishing students' grounding in core physics concepts. This paper emphasizes that DL should complement, rather than replace, the existing focus areas within the physics curriculum.

Under these circumstances, allocating large amounts of ECTS (European Credit Transfer System) credit points specifically for DL and RDM is difficult, as it goes along with reducing credit allocations for other important subjects. To address this, the proposed curriculum integration aims to embed DL and RDM training strategically, in ways that enhance existing courses rather than requiring large numbers of entirely new modules. Specifically, this plan identifies five natural points of integration:

1. initial programming and data handling course
2. beginner's lab courses
3. advanced lab courses
4. bachelor's thesis
5. master's thesis

By aligning DL training with these existing milestones, students can be equipped with essential skills requiring little ECTS reallocation and without sacrificing critical components of the traditional physics education. The RDM competence levels associated to the Bloom [10] scale (1: Remembering, 2: Understanding, 3: Applying, 4: Analyzing, 5: Evaluating, 6: Creating) are acquired in various cycles, with increasing width of skills. In the subsequent section, we assign the Bloom levels, where applicable.

4 Proposed curriculum integration

Mandatory introduction in the first semester. As a prerequisite of this overall transformation, we recommend an introduction at the beginning of the first semester (Bloom level 1-2), where every student has taken over responsibility for a running programming environment, some fundamental concepts like data handling, visualization, application

of simple functions, and fitting routines. This might be part of the first lecture in *Experimental Physics*, like at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, or a dedicated course in *Data handling in physics*, like at Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. It does not need much to start, if subsequent courses take over and further sharpen these skills. This encourages both the lecturers and tutors, but also the students to actively apply data literacy programming tools in regular courses with minimal threshold (Bloom level 3). It is important to note that one should not overload course programs by simultaneously introducing new physics and new data handling content. By experience, there are parts of the first semester physics which are sufficiently familiar to the students that they can easily ingest additional programming and data handling exercises.

Ubiquitous emphasis on data. With this fundamental background in Python programming, and potentially other modern programming languages like Julia, our teaching might be reoriented towards data at many occasions: Traditional exercises in kinematics, like the free fall, might be calculated numerically from a given data set rather than from a single set of given parameters. Experiments that are conducted with analog measurement equipment like a stopwatch, a ruler, a pointer instrument or a liquid-in-glass thermometer might be suitable for school, but may be abandoned to give space for data-related techniques. Similarly, a classical pocket calculator error analysis in lab courses might be replaced by digital data acquisition and suitable python routines. We encourage to watch out for such opportunities in the current course programs, and to solve them coherently by employing Python tools (Bloom level 3).

In this way, we give the students a tool at hand with which they can overcome restrictions that many of us experienced in our early years. Just to mention a few examples: Students often mistrust mathematical approximations. They can now check by numerical methods under which conditions the approximations are well justified (Bloom level 4-5). Numerical methods also enlarge the portfolio of possible problems that can be treated in more advanced exercises in solid state physics, particle physics, optics, etc., which were inaccessible beforehand. Furthermore, data visualization allows for a playful approach to physical problems (Bloom level 6). By experience, this benefit to all courses in the physics curriculum becomes only possible if there is a general consensus about the programming language and about the software tools used. Only in this way, students can concentrate on the underlying physics and have a step-by-step learning in programming skills. As a matter of fact, when all stakeholders in teaching, that is students, tutors and lecturers, use more and more numerical tools, there is an increase in competence for all of them.

Beginner's lab courses. The Beginner's lab course is often not fully appreciated by the students, because it largely revisits knowledge that they already learned in school. When applying digital data treatment as an additional part of the lab course, it is conceived as something new and more interesting. This may apply, for example, to the introduction of statistical methods and error analysis, often being a first unit of the beginner's lab course. In coordination with the first-semester data and programming course, this evaluation

can be performed numerically such that data treatment and extraction of statistical quantities are increasing the students' capabilities (Bloom level 3-5). Whether or not computer-controlled data acquisition or manual acquisition is preferred, is probably not crucial at this stage.

Accurate documentation of the experiment and the evaluation is also a key competence that should be acquired in beginner's lab courses (Bloom level 1-3). We recommend Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs)¹ instead of traditional pen and paper solutions as today's standard. Moreover, it encourages also an immediate evaluation, which in turn gives a quick feedback whether or not the experiment was successful and the data are meaningful. ELNs are typically cloud solutions where the student team shares the same information at any time, and all data (preparation, notes, measured data, evaluation) are at the same location. Furthermore, with the possibility of electronic access to data stored in the ELN, sources of mistakes and inconsistencies within the team are strongly reduced.

Advanced lab courses While in the beginner's lab courses, the ELNs may be prestructured such that the students are appropriately guided through the experiments, this guidance can be reduced in advanced lab courses such that more and more responsibility is given to the students (Bloom level 4-6). This includes planning of the experiment and data acquisition, appropriate preparation of ELN entries and documentation of the measurement protocol. It is an opportunity to advise the students about the importance of metadata and to introduce the FAIR principles. We would encourage the lab course supervisors to consider agreement with international standards. An obvious example is to store physical quantities consequently with units which could either follow community standards or SI units. As an example, in an X-ray diffraction experiment, Ångström is the unit of choice whereas the SI expects meters. In a modern ELN, the students should be supported by built-in automatic unit conversion. As a guideline, the usage of ELNs in advanced lab courses should prepare the students for the documentation of real-life research data. Students should understand that immediate and meaningful documentation helps not only in lab courses, but also in view of later research projects to simplify their work and enable creative thinking based on a solid documentation. With these steps, the students take over ownership on their data in agreement with the expectation of modern science [16].

Advanced lab courses are also suitable to systematically introduce electronic data acquisition (Bloom level 3). This is more than a technical competence, because responsibility for the experimental protocol and the data creation are transferred to the students. For example, the selection of suitable instruments and measurement ranges, the order of data recording in orchestrated many-instrument setups and the overall measurement time have to be carefully balanced. This choice has immediate influence on the data quality and accuracy and is, hence, indispensable part of the documentation. Structured data file formats like HDF5 [17] can accommodate both, raw data and metadata,

¹Recommended open-source software for Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN): eLabFTW [11, 12], NOMAD Oasis [7, 13], openBIS [14, 15]

Table 1: Condensed summary of proposed curriculum changes for DL and RDM. The students increase their competence and ownership on data.

Stage	Core proposed changes
First semester	Compact introduction to Python and data handling using a unified programming environment; integrate simple data tasks into familiar physics topics.
Ubiquitous data emphasis	Use numerical methods broadly; replace old-fashioned methods with Python analysis.
Beginner’s lab courses	Use numerical data handling; use electronic lab notebooks (ELNs); encourage immediate digital documentation and evaluation.
Advanced lab courses	Increase student responsibility in ELNs; teach metadata and FAIR principles; adopt structured data formats (HDF5); integrate systematic electronic data acquisition.
Bachelor’s / master’s theses	Apply ELN/RDM practices in research groups; promote FAIR data sharing; store complete datasets in (internal) repositories.

and should replace simple raw data-only formats such as CSV.

In addition, we encourage dedicated data-oriented experiments that take data from external sources like *HEPData* [5], *NOMAD* [6, 7] or *Zenodo* [18] in order to perform numerical analyses on shared data.

Bachelor’s and master’s thesis We are in a transition phase where many groups have not yet established RDM standards. Therefore, students with ELN and data expertise bring additional skills into the groups which might support the modification of the everyday data workflow (Bloom level 6).

In the research context, students are confronted with the challenge of data sharing within the group or in collaborations. Here, the FAIR principles, particularly the interoperability aspect, may be understood as a useful concept to share data efficiently. We emphasize that there are by now ELN and RDM tools available that support this way of data oriented research. The choice of appropriate tools is usually at the discretion of the research groups.

Frequently, the bachelor’s thesis is the first scientific publication in a student’s career. It is an opportunity to store the entire research data in a repository, which could be in-house. Only when the data are FAIR, other group members can reuse the data meaningfully. Hence the training to FAIR data does not necessarily require open-science repositories, but may start in a confidential environment.

5 Best-practice examples

The following example modules are intended to serve as a source of inspiration and a concrete proposal that incorporates best practices in DL and RDM. By providing these examples, we aim to illustrate how foundational and advanced concepts in data handling, reproducibility, and data sharing can be integrated effectively at various stages in the physics curriculum.

5.1 Introductory module: Data handling in physics

A module *Data handling in physics* serves as a foundational course for bachelor’s students, specifically designed to introduce essential concepts in DL and RDM. This module equips students with practical skills in data handling, scientific programming, and statistical analysis in a hands-on format. Through simulations and exercises in Jupyter Notebooks, students learn programming basics, data storage techniques, and essential statistical methods, using languages and tools such as Python, Julia, and libraries like NumPy, SciPy and Matplotlib.

Such a module is, for example, offered as an obligatory module *Datenverarbeitung in der Physik*² at the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg [19], or as an optional course *Grundlagen wissenschaftlicher Datenverarbeitung am Computer*³ [20] at the Technische Universität Dortmund.

In Erlangen, key topics include, besides a solid introduction into Python and its scientific computing ecosystem, topics such as data visualisation, statistical data analysis and model fitting, data interpolation, numerical integration and solutions to simple differential equations, introduction to image processing and symbolic mathematics as well as good scientific practice. In Dortmund, emphasis is given on data generation through simulations, data storage as structured and unstructured data, principles of data compression, and foundational techniques for error estimation, statistical modeling, and data visualization. In addition, students receive an introduction to best practices for data documentation, reproducibility, and ethical data handling, aligned with the FAIR principles.

5.2 Integration of data literacy in the foundational experimental physics course

Another opportunity of introducing similar content is to integrate programming exercises in the foundational experimental physics course. Here, conventional first-semester (e. g. mechanics and thermodynamics) physics problems are posed as small programming tasks using, for example, the CodeRunner module within the learning platform Moodle. In our experience the students are able to learn the necessary programming skills autodidactically and ‘en-passant’, if the speed at which new programming concepts are introduced is kept low. In our experience, it works well to start the first two weeks by

²English translation: Data Handling in Physics

³English translation: Fundamentals of Scientific Data Handling on a Computer

asking them to assign the numerical result of a physics problem to a variable. In subsequent weeks, they will be asked to print their result as a formatted string, including the unit, write simple functions which will then be called with different parameters, use lists, dictionaries, numpy arrays, etc. Each week only one new concept should be introduced. We found it very helpful to allow the students to let CodeRunner pre-validate their answers arbitrarily many times, before submitting. This gives them immediate feedback on their answers and allows them to converge to the right result by themselves - maximizing the learning effect of both the new programming concepts, as well as the particular physics problem they are solving. After having practiced this way of posing homework problems for several years, there has been very positive feedback, despite the fact that the actual programming techniques are not addressed in any of the lectures. They are only described in accompanying jupyter notebooks, with examples that can be referred to when converting their answer to the physics to python code. The Jupyter notebooks with example calculations for some of the physics phenomena discussed in the course are regularly mentioned positively in the course evaluations.

5.3 Introduction of electronic lab notebooks in physics lab courses

Quite naturally, the lab courses are the place within the curriculum where the students take over responsibility of their data. In Erlangen, electronic lab notebooks (ELN)⁴ were introduced in the regular lab courses in the 4th semester in 2022. A cloud-based open-source ELN was established as a central university service [21]. The usual group of two students share the same ELN entries, which are prestructured along the experiment instructions. Each ELN entry includes (i) the documentation of the preparation, (ii) the experiment description, (iii) the results and observations, (iv) data files, (v) the documentation of analyses including the Jupyter scripts developed and used, and (vi) the final presentation of the evaluated data. The access to data stored in the ELN was simplified by one-line Python commands provided by a dedicated Python package [22]. Thus, students could immediately apply their skills obtained in the introductory module (cf. 5.1) to their electronically available experimental data in the ELN. The students immediately adapted this new toolbox to a more collaborative, data-oriented working style both within the team of two and with the tutors. An early and more detailed description is given in Ref. [19].

At Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, a similar concept has been implemented, giving the students the option of using a different open-source ELN (NOMAD Oasis), or acquire the data directly within the Jupyter notebook they also use for their analysis. For this purpose, a library is supplied which provides ipywidgets [23] to generate a table with the desired columns and choice of units, storing the data as HDF5 files and giving the option of creating additional tables with the same columns and units as one of the already existing HDF5 files they have generated. Some potentially useful table templates are already pre-defined. This tool helps the students to internalize the concept of data

⁴We started with the ELN software openBIS [14, 15], since 2024 we have been using eLabFTW [11, 12].

schemas. By employing a consistent data schema (including units and accompanying metadata) for the different datasets, the efficient re-use of the students' code for data handling becomes possible.

For the subsequent advanced lab courses, the students increasingly take over responsibility for structuring their data in the ELN. This paves the way for employing ELNs productively in their own research project in the bachelor's and master's thesis. Four years after the ELN introduction, ELN competencies have reached all workgroups at the department.

5.4 Advanced data-swapping exercise for lab courses

Many promising concepts exist to mentally anchor the idea of reproducibility (see e. g. [24]). In a similar spirit, but using means that integrate naturally with other physics courses, the *Data-Swapping Exercise* introduces students to the practice of sharing, interpreting, and reusing data from external sources, enshrining the FAIR principles in their work experience. As students progress through their studies, this exercise can be implemented within advanced lab courses, allowing them to experience the challenges of working with datasets they did not generate themselves. The exercise emphasizes the importance of clear documentation and metadata standards, as students exchange datasets with their peers and attempt to reproduce and expand upon each other's findings.

A first implementation of such a data-swapping exercise at the TU Dortmund has found resounding success, allowing students to gain firsthand experience with the practical requirements of the FAIR principles in a collaborative research setting. For this exercise, student groups in the advanced lab courses were required to exchange their datasets between the groups for one experiment, each group pairing up with a partner group who conducted the same experiment and the data of which they were required to analyze instead of their own. Notably, this exercise was conducted as a surprise to the students, such that they were able to experience first-hand the difference between working with data they have themselves collected, and the data collection and documentation performed by their peers.

By incorporating this exercise into the advanced lab courses, students not only build technical competency in data analysis but also learn collaborative data management skills crucial for interdisciplinary research. This approach reinforces the importance of transparent and ethical data practices while providing practical experience in a controlled, educational environment, preparing students to effectively manage, share, and use data in real-world research settings.

For future applications, resources such as *HEPData* [5] and *Zenodo* [18] may serve as additional data sources for analysis practice, allowing students to familiarize themselves with these repositories and develop skills in both uploading their own datasets and navigating existing ones.

5.5 A course on using the virtual observatory

The Virtual Observatory (VO) [25] is a comprehensive data infrastructure in astrophysics and astroparticle physics. As such, it is also a complex system, currently used by astronomers either behind several abstraction levels or by taking specialised, pre-written workflows and warily adapting them for their immediate requirements, which often results in sub-optimal solutions severely falling short of exploiting the full power of the VO.

This is what the semester-long course on using the VO [26] – given first at Universität Heidelberg in the summer semester 2024 – sets out to change by giving the participants a solid understanding of the architecture, protocols, and clients of the VO.

There are two large focus blocks within the course: One on the VO’s major query language, ADQL, a dialect of SQL, that also introduces students to the concepts of relational algebra, designed to be given in three or four sessions [27]. The second focus block is on pyVO, a Python-based API to the VO’s facilities, which can be given in between four and nine sessions, depending on what optional topics are included [28]. The two courses are also available separately for block courses addressing persons with pre-existing VO skills.

Additional material delving more deeply into specific and overarching topics is available as side tracks that can float or, in part, be skipped in a concrete course.

The material is accompanied by exercises with solutions, with the intention of making the lecture notes also useful for self-study. The target audience is graduate students – a certain amount of astronomy knowledge is assumed, as well as basic python skills for the pyVO part –, doctoral students, and, at least in block course format, researchers.

5.6 Course for master’s and doctoral students: Experiments and data at photon and neutron facilities

A lecture series has been established at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) to educate on research data management and FAIR data principles [29, 30]. This lecture series provides weekly online lectures and is organized by the DAPHNE4NFDI consortium. The course aims at introducing several common experimental techniques being used at large-scales facilities, i. e. neutron sources and synchrotrons, and the associated data aspects. The lectures not only provide an introduction to FAIR data principles but also cover specific experimental methods. Hence, the participants learn about new spectroscopic, imaging or scattering techniques and at the same time data-related topics. Each session highlights different issues, associated with scientific examples, underlining the importance of metadata, data publication, electronic laboratory notebooks, repositories, and reference databases. In addition, hands-on data management and FAIR workflows at large-scale facilities are taught. Furthermore, the challenges and opportunities of properly and efficiently handling the large datasets produced during experiments are addressed, including improved research data management, the automatic ingestion of metadata, and artificial intelligence and machine learning models.

The lecture series is currently integrated at the master’s and doctoral level. It com-

prises 16 modules and can be formally recognized with 2 ECTS credits. At KIT, the lecture series is already established as an official course offering. Participation certificates documenting the awarded ECTS credits are provided to students. Depending on local curriculum structures, such lecture series may either be integrated as optional domain-specific training within master's programs or embedded more formally into structured graduate education programs. It represents the first course lecture of its kind.

5.7 Using NOMAD Oasis and NORTH tools for bachelor's and master's theses

Creating an ELN entry within a NOMAD Oasis for every new bachelor's or master's thesis and asking the student to store and process their files within this space allows seamless interaction between student and supervisor, because they have a common space to visualize the data, process the data with the same software tools that are configured to run as a tool within the NOMAD Remote Tools Hub (NORTH), and discuss the latest stage of the analysis and documentation, e. g. in form of a Jupyter Notebook. Once the thesis is completed, all the data generated and processed for it is already stored in the (local) NOMAD Oasis database and can later be searched for by people who have been configured to have access to it. It can also be published on the local NOMAD Oasis or even globally, with the push of a button.

6 Existing RDM training and support structures in Germany

The best practice examples described in the previous sections are partly enabled on a technical level by RDM support units at the respective institutions, and/or the national consortia that are authors of this manuscript. This includes the provision of professionally serviced RDM tools, train-the-trainer programs, and interdisciplinary cooperations.

One best-practice example is established at the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU): the Competence Center for Research Data and Information (CDI) [21]. This unit operates and provides various ELNs as a central service, accessible to any student and researcher via single-sign-on, and offers training, customization and every-day support. As a consequence, homogeneous environments for teaching- and research-related RDM is available without bothering lecturers and researchers with server and software administration. As a commitment to teaching, basic ELN services for teaching are provided without costs at FAU.

We appreciate the growing support of university libraries and computing centers for the support of the integration of data literacy and RDM throughout Germany.

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